

Jek Londonning “Hayotga muhabbat” hikoyasida hayotsevarlik g’oyalari

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Kalit so‘zlar: hikoya, qahramon, hayotsevarlik, oltin izlovchi, “Berdferd” kemasi, Bill,

Annotatsiya: Maqolada Jek Londonning “Hayotga muhabbat” hikoyasi g’oyalari tahlil qilinadi. Asarni adabiyot mashg‘ulotlarida o‘rganish va uning kitobxonga beradigan tarbiyaviy omillari ochib beriladi. Insonning o‘zi tomon shiddat bilan yaqinlashib kelayotagan o‘lim vahimasini jasorat bilan yengishi, uning optimistik qarashlari tahlil qilinadi.

1876-1916-yillarda yashagan Jek London 150 dan ortiq hikoyalar yozgan. Shulardan biri kitobxonni hayotsevarlikka undovchi “Hayotga muhabbat” hikoyasidir. Unda insonning hayotga bo‘lgan muhabbat yo‘lidagi mashaqqatli kechinmalari o‘z aksini topadi. Hikoya qahramoni bu yo‘lda uni tinimsiz tuzog‘iga tushirmoqchi bo‘lgan o‘limni katta matonat bilan yengadi. Unda ikki oltin izlovchi qahramonning ayanchli taqdiri badiiy tasvirlanadi. Qahramonlardan biri Bill ismli o‘ta xudbin, xiyonatkori, ochko‘z tip sifatida gavdalantiriladi. U o‘z xasisligi sababli do‘stini aro yo‘lda qoldirib, oltinlarini orqalab, orqasiga hatto qayrilib ham qaramasdan ketib qoladi. Do‘sti esa kasal va nochor holatda uning ortidan umid bilan termulib qoladi. Har bir zamonda ham topidib turadigan bunday qahramonlar kitobxon ongida nafrat va unga achinish hissini uyg‘otadi. Bunday holatga tushib qolmaslik, ya‘ni o‘z dustini, yaqinlarini nochor tashlab ketmaslik kerakligini uqtiradi.

Shunday qilib kasal va ojiz bir umid bilan Billning ortidan qarab qolgan qahramonimiz bu kimsasiz biyobondan albatta tirik chiqish maqsadini o‘z oldiga qo‘yadi. Xasta hoida bir amallab dardga, ob-havo injiqliklariga, ochlikka bardosh berib, yirtqich hayvonlarga yem bo‘lishdan o‘zini himoya qilib kit ovlovchi “Berdferd” kemasidagi ilmiy ekspedisiya a‘zolari huzuriga yetib keladi. Kemadagilar uni ilk bor qirg‘oqda ko‘rib qolganlarida g‘alati bir maxluq deb o‘ylashadi. Chunki og‘riqli dardlardan, ochlik va tashnalikdan tinkasi qurigan, ustidagi kiyimlari titilib ketgan, soch soqoli o‘sgan, tanasi uzoq vaqt suv ko‘rmaganidan, eng dahshatlisi o‘t-o‘lanlarni, xom baliqlarni, bo‘rilar g‘ajib

tashlagan suyaklarni yeganligidan ivirsib ketgan zotni haqiqatan ham tanish amrimahol bo‘lib qolgan edi. Lekin bu qahramon aynan hayotga bo‘lgan cheksiz muhabbati tufayli tirik qolgan edi. Buni sharq maqollariga ko‘ra “Ajali yetmagan bo‘lsa qirq yil qirg‘in kelsa ham omon qoladi”, degan ibora bilan izohlashimiz mumkin. Yigit har qancha og‘ir bo‘lmasin, qiyinchiliklarni yengib o‘tishga, faqat oldinga intilishga, yashash uchun kurashga intiladi. Shu intilish uni o‘limdan saqlab qoladi.

Ushbu hikoyaning badiiy qimmatini shundaki, unda inson irodasi, matonati va chidami madh etiladi. Unda inson umidi achchiq haqiqat bilan hisoblashishni istamasligi, qo‘rquv yashash uchun kurash matonati bilan chambarchas bog‘liq ekanligi g‘oyalari ochib berilgan. Hikoyada aytilishicha, odam hayot uchun kurashmay qo‘ysa-da, undagi hayotning o‘zi o‘lishni istamaydi. Shuning uchun ham odamni faqat ilgariga undaydi.

Hikoyada och va xayollarini o‘lim qo‘rquvi egallab olgan insonning ruhiy holati, orzu intilishlari, hatti-harakati psixologik jihatdan juda ta’sirli yoritib berilgan. Och oltin izlovchi yo‘lida uchragan har bir ko‘lmakdagi kichkina baliqchani tutib yemoqchi bo‘ladi. Ammo ko‘lmak suvi loyqalanib, u baliqchani tutolmaydi. Shunda u qo‘lidagi paqirchasi bilan ko‘lmak suvini olib to‘ka boshlaydi. Suvni to‘kib bo‘lib qarasa, baliqcha yo‘q. Baliqcha ko‘lmak tubidagi teshik orqali boshqa ko‘lmakka o‘tib ketgan ekan. Ana shunda oltin izlovchi qilgan mehnati zoye ketganiga achinib, ilk bor yig‘lab yuboradi.

Hikoya qahramoni bo‘rilar yaqindagina g‘ajib ketgan yosh bug‘uning suyaklarini ochlikka chidolmay yirtqich hayvonlar misoli g‘ajiy boshlaydi. Hatto tishlari sinib ketsa ham parvo qilmaydi. Sekin-asta emaklab kema ko‘ringan hududga kelay deb qolganda unga tashlangan och va kasal bo‘rini ham tishlab o‘ldiradi, uning qonini ichadi. Bundan hatto jirkanmaydi ham. Mazkur holatda inson tirik qolish uchun, hayot uchun unda umid va xohish bo‘lsa, albatta bu yo‘lda g‘olib bo‘la oladi. Bu o‘rinda u o‘zining insoniy sifatlarini ham yo‘qotib borayotgan edi. Biroq oltin izlovchi o‘z yo‘lida bevafo do‘sti Billning bo‘rilar tomonidan g‘ajilgan suyaklariga duch kelganida har qancha och bo‘lmasin, odam suyagini g‘ajishdan o‘zini tiyishga kuch topa oladi. U hatto Billning oltinlarini ham olmaydi. Bu uning uchun hayotda uchrashi mumkin bo‘lgan kurashlarning eng shiddatlisi edi. Lekin asar qahramoni buni yengib o‘ta oladi. U ochlik va og‘riqdan qurtdek buralib qolgan bo‘lsa-da, faqat oldinga siljishga harakat qiladi. Orqaga qaytishni yoki to‘xtab qolishni sira xayoliga keltirmaydi. U buralib-buralib harakat qiladi va soatiga atigi 20 qadamdan yo‘l bosar edi.

Odamlar orasiga kelib qo‘shilgan bu zot ancha vaqtgacha o‘nglana olmay yuradi. Uni ochlik xavotiri tinimsiz tashvishga solib turadi. Aqli joyida bo‘lsa ham stol atrofiga ovqatlanish uchun yig‘ilgan odamlarga faqat nafrat ko‘zi bilan qaray boshlaydi. Uni ovqatning tamom bo‘lib qolishi juda tashvishga soladi. Karavotining ostini suxarilar bilan to‘ldirib tashlaydi. Yana och qolib qiyin vaziyatlarga tushib qolishdan qattiq qo‘rqadi. Ammo uning bu ruhiy holatini kemadagilar to‘g‘ri tushunadilar va manzilga yetib borgach, ko‘p insonlar bilan muloqot qilish natijasida bu kasallikdan qutuladi. Ushbu hikoya o‘z kitobxonida dastlab shunday og‘ir vaziyatga tushib qolgan insonning matonati hayratga soladi. Ochlik va xastalik, qo‘rquv va charchoq tuyg‘ularini oddiygina yashashga, hayotga bo‘lgan muhabbat bilangina yengib bilganini ko‘rishimiz mumkin. Hayotda juda ko‘plab insonlarning oddiy tashvishlardan tushkunlikka tushib, o‘z jonlariga qasd qilishlari bilan bu holatni solishtirib bo‘lmaydi. Biri tengi yo‘q jasoratdan dars bersa, biri o‘ta tubanlik – o‘zining bebaho boyligi, yaxshi ishlar, savob ishlar qilib qolish uchun berilgan imkoniyatdan foydalana olmaslik ilmidan dars berishini ko‘ramiz. Shu jihatdan bu hikoya insonlarda hayotda tushkunlikka tushmaslik, har bir ishni muhabbat va sadoqat bilan, hayotni sevgan holda bajarish lozimligini uqtiradi. Umuman olganda hayotni sevishga, uni ardoqlashga undovchi mazkur hikoya ko‘plab kitobxonlar hayotini oftobdek yorita oladi.

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